

PSYCHOLOGICAL BASES FOR INTENSIFICATION OF LEARNING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT THE INITIAL STAGE

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Abstract. *The article analyzes the psychological foundations of the intensification of teaching a foreign language at primary school age. It also examines the basics of communicative competence, which are necessary and sufficient for their further development and improvement in the course of studying that subject. A foreign language lesson has its own specifics, since, unlike other subjects, the formation of the communicative competence of students is put forward as the main goal of learning. At present, the global goal of mastering a foreign language is considered to be the introduction to another culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved through the formation of the ability for intercultural communication.*

Keywords: *competence, psychological foundations, teaching a foreign language, primary school, teacher.*

A foreign language lesson has its own specifics, since, unlike other subjects, the formation of students' communicative competence is put forward as the main goal of learning. At present, the global goal of mastering a foreign language is considered to be familiarization with a different culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures. This goal is achieved through the formation of the ability to intercultural communication. It is teaching, organized on the basis of tasks of a communicative nature, teaching foreign language communication, using all the tasks and techniques necessary for this, that is a distinctive feature of a foreign language lesson [1].

The experiments of recent years have confirmed that foreign language classes develop children, first of all, their logical thinking, raise their educational and cultural level, there is a positive effect of learning a foreign language on knowledge of their native language. The duration of the sensitive, i.e. psychologists interpret the most favorable period for learning a foreign language in different ways, but most often they converge on the period from 4 to 8 years. Physiologists believe that there is a biological clock of the brain, just as there are stages in the development of the endocrine glands of the child in time. A child under 9 years old is a specialist in mastering speech. After this period, the brain mechanisms of speech become less flexible and cannot easily adapt to new conditions. After 10 years, the child has to overcome many additional obstacles. The child's brain has a specialized ability for language acquisition, but this decreases with age. The speed and strength of memorization of foreign language material at this age is explained both by the predominance of long-term memory mechanisms and by the presence of imprinting (imprinting of material into consciousness, provided that the necessary stimulus and motivation are present).

The initial stage in secondary school is understood as the period of learning a foreign language, which allows laying the foundations of communicative competence, necessary and sufficient for their further development and improvement in the course of studying that subject.

In this manual, we refer classes I-IV of general educational institutions to the initial stage. To lay the foundations of communicative competence, a sufficiently long period is required, because students need to familiarize themselves with the language being studied as a means of communication from the first steps.

This means that they must learn to understand foreign speech by ear (listening), express their thoughts by means of the language being studied (speaking), read, that is, understand a foreign text read to themselves, and write, that is, learn to use the graphics and spelling of a foreign language when performing written tasks aimed at mastering reading and speaking, or be able to express their thoughts in writing [2].

In addition, it is at the initial stage that the methodological system that forms the basis of teaching a foreign language is implemented, which from the first steps allows the teacher to enter this system and carry out the educational process in accordance with its main provisions [3].

All researchers argue that education should be focused on the psychophysiological age characteristics of children. It has been proved that special classes in a foreign language can be started with children 4-10 years old: up to 4 years old it makes no sense, and after 10 years old it is useless to hope for a positive result. It is best to start learning a foreign language at the age of 5-8 years, when the system of the native language is well mastered, and a conscious attitude has already been formed towards the new language. It is at this age that there are still few speech clichés, it is easy to rebuild one's thoughts on a new construction and there are no great difficulties when making contact in a foreign language. And if the methodological system is built correctly from the linguodidactic and psycholinguistic points of view, then success in mastering the proposed limited speech material and creating the necessary prerequisites for further mastering a foreign language is ensured by almost all children.

Early learning a foreign language contributes not only to a more solid and fluent command of it, but also carries a great intellectual, educational and moral potential.

Early language learning:

- stimulates the speech and general development of children and increases the general educational value of primary education, as the foundation of general education;
- introduces children to the culture of other nations, thereby forming a universal consciousness;
- creates a favorable initial base for mastering a foreign language, as well as for further language learning, since the formation of psychological barriers that arise during the initial teaching of a foreign language at the age of 1-11 years is prevented;
- provides the possibility of earlier completion of the study of the first language and connection of the second;
- improves general skills (ability to work with a book, reference literature);
- forms special learning skills (the ability to work with a bilingual dictionary) [4].

Since foreign language communication is based on the theory of speech activity. Communicative teaching of a foreign language is of an activity nature, since verbal communication is carried out through "speech activity", which, in turn, serves to solve the problems of productive human activity in the conditions of "social interaction" of communicating people. Participants of communication try to solve real and imaginary tasks of joint activity with the help of a foreign language.

With this approach, positive conditions are created for the active and free development of the individual in activity. In general, these conditions are as follows:

- students get the opportunity to freely express their thoughts and feelings in the process of communication;
- each participant of communication remains in focus of attention of the others;
- participants in communication feel safe from criticism, prosecution for mistakes and punishment.

It should be noted that with a competent construction of a methodological system from a linguodidactic and psycholinguistic point of view, success in mastering the proposed limited speech material and creating the necessary prerequisites for further assimilation of a foreign language is ensured by almost all children[5]. The effect of learning a foreign language at primary school age will certainly have a positive impact on the development of children, the culture of communication, will influence the activation of all mental functions, and will expand the general horizons of children.

Summing up the above, it is necessary to emphasize the importance of the interaction and cooperation of students, as well as the speech task for organizing communicative language acquisition. Communicative learning includes the formation of a communicative concept, that is, internal readiness and ability for verbal communication, orienting students to “enter” into a different cultural space. Such training is characterized, first of all, by non-traditional forms of conducting classes.

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